

Chan Buddhism in the Song

By Xuejing Sun, USC

Entry tags: Religious Group, Chinese Religion, Chan Buddhism (chan zong 禪宗), Chinese Buddhist Traditions, Yellow and Yangzi Rivers Region

Originating from the early Mahayanian meditation (Skr. Dyana) practices, Chan禪 Buddhism gradually developed into a highly indigenous form in China since the sixth century. A famous, yet simplistic, four-part motto adapted from the Platform Sutra has been widely used by Chan communities to characterize the Chan ideology: "special transmission outside the scriptures; not established upon words; directly pointing to human heart-mind; realizing the Buddhahood by seeing one's Buddha-nature." Chinese Chan Buddhism reached new heights during the Song. Unlike the decline of many Buddhist schools following the unrest of the late-Tang period (mid 8th-9th cent.), the Chan school continued to gain popularity during the turmoil times of the Five Dynasties and Ten Kingdoms (907-979). To enhance their political regimes, regional rulers in southern China began to sponsor, instead of individual monks, multiple generations of Chan masters belonging to the same lineage. This pattern of state endorsement of Chan lineage families, institutions, and literature continued into the new dynasty of Song, which became a hallmark of Song Chan Buddhism. The picture of a "Golden Age of Chan" embodied by noble Tang masters as painted in Chan literature has led to a long-standing stereotype that deterioration characterized much of the Song Chan Buddhism. However, behind such narratives reconstructed by the Song authors, modern scholars have begun to acknowledge that it was during the Song that the Chan school took its fully mature form. Intellectual and artistic achievements associated with Song Chan Buddhism have significantly enhanced Chinese culture in general. New developments within Song Chan Buddhism have had a profound impact on the Chan traditions (Jpn. Zen; Krn. Seon) throughout East Asia. Compared to its earlier stages, Song Chan Buddhism presented many new features that would continue to dominate the Chinese religious landscape for several more centuries. First and foremost, Song Chan Buddhism distinguished itself by the advent and expansion of new styles of Chan literature: Gong'an公案 (Jpn. Koan), or "public cases," are short stories of a Chan master's commentaries on a previous dialogue or vignette of a past Chan patriarch. Gong'an became a standardized Chan literature genre from the eleventh century and was used largely as a pedagogical tool to elicit doubt and sudden enlightenment from the disciples. Yulu語錄, or "recorded sayings," documents the sayings of great Chan masters and were popular among both monastic communities and elite sponsors. Qinggui清規, or "rules of purity," provides detailed guidance for Chan monastic life. Denglu燈錄, or "lamp histories," are narratives of a fairly coherent Chan family lineage starting from the Sakyamuni Buddha to Bodhidharma, down to the Chan masters of the Song. It was from such abundant literature that a distinct "Chan" identity emerged, emphasizing the lineage transmissions and the master-disciple relations. Second, Chan Buddhism during the Song maintained unusual relations with the imperial circles. The compilation of Chan literature, especially that of the denglu燈錄, was under the collaboration of Chan communities and high court officials, often entitled with the name of a particular imperial era. It was also during the Song that public monasteries (as opposed to private hereditary monasteries where the succeeding abbacies could be decided by private sponsors and the current abbots) of Chan began to receive state sponsorship, official recognition, and political regulation with their abbacies appointed by the government. Third, while many sects -among which the Yunmen雲門, Linji臨濟, and Caodong曹洞 were the most dominant- coexisted during the Song, in comparison with the competent histories of Tang Chan (especially the confrontation between the "Southern" and "Northern" schools), Song Chan Buddhism displayed a non-sectarian nature in general. The major doctrinal dispute, however, was perhaps the different approaches to enlightenment between Mozhao默照, "silent-illumination" (enlightenment through silent meditation) and Kanhua看話, "reflection on gong'an" (enlightenment through concentration on gong'an stories), which were advocated by sects of Caodong (Jpn. Soto) and Linji (Jpn. Rinzai) respectively. Despite doctrinal differences, the rise and fall of Song Chan lineages, as suggested by recent scholarship,

were more closely associated with the change of regional sponsor networks. Fourth, apart from its distinct lineage identities, the Chan school shared common monastic practices and rituals with other contemporaneous Buddhist groups. The syncretistic tendencies of Song Chan Buddhism—especially with the Pure Land practices—would continue through the Yuan (1271-1368) and became more prominent in Ming (1368-1644) Chan Buddhism.

Date Range: 960 CE - 1279 CE

Region: Active regions of Song Chan Buddhism

Region tags: China, Jiangsu Province, Zhejiang, Yangzi River Valley

Major public Chan monasteries of the Southern Song dynasty (1127-1279) concentrated in the Jiangnan area. The abbacy of Chan masters from lineages of Yunmen, Caodong, Linji, and Fayan also spread around the Northern Song (960-1127) capital city of Kaifeng and along the middle and upper Yangtze River throughout the Song period. For a critical study on the geographic history of Song Chan Buddhism, see Jason Protass, "A geographic History of Song-Dynasty Chan Buddhism," *Asia Major* (2019) 3d ser. Vol. 32.1: 113-60.

参与者的状态

✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家

来源

理解这一问题的书面资料：

- 来源 1: Morten Schlutter. *How Zen Became Zen: The Dispute over Enlightenment and the Formation of Chan Buddhism in Song-dynasty China*. University of Hawaii Press, 2008.
- 来源 2: Heinrich Dumoulin. *Zen Buddhism, India and China*. 1988. Reprinted, World Wisdom Inc, 2005.
- 来源 3: John R. McRae. *Seeing through Zen: Encounter, Transformation, and Genealogy in Chinese Chan Buddhism*. University of California Press, 2004.

Reference: Brose, Benjamin. *Patrons and Patriarchs*. University of Hawaii Press, 2015.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=91cEEAAQBAJ>.

Reference: Cole, Alan. *Patriarchs on Paper*. University of California Press, 2016.
https://books.google.com/books/about/Patriarchs_on_Paper.html?hl=&id=nisoDQAAQBAJ.

Reference: Yü, Chün-fang, and Daniel B. Stevenson. *The Renewal of Buddhism in China - Zhuhong and the Late Ming Synthesis*, 2020.
https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Renewal_of_Buddhism_in_China_Zhuhong.html?hl=&id=Q8x2zQEACAAJ.

理解这一问题的在线资料:

- 来源1 URL: <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/buddhism-chan/>

相关的在线的原始文本资料库(使用原语言和/或翻译)

—来源1 URL: <https://cbetaonline.cn/en/>

—来源2 URL: <https://21dzk.l.u-tokyo.ac.jp/SAT/satdb2015.php?lang=en>

一般变量

成员/团体互动

其他宗教团体与该宗教之间有文化上的接触吗：

—是

Notes: The other Buddhist groups that coexisted with Chan during the Song include Tiantai, Huayan, Pure Land, and Vinaya Schools. Besides, there were also Daoist groups, Confucian communities and popular religious groups in competition and also in communication with Chan.

Reference: Getz, Daniel A., and Peter N. Gregory. *Buddhism in the Sung*. University of Hawaii Press, 2002. https://books.google.com/books/about/Buddhism_in_the_Sung.html?hl=&id=nYdOnj41h-AC.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 960 CE - 1276 CE

↳ 这种文化接触是竞争性的吗：

—是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 960 CE - 1276 CE

↳ 文化接触是兼容并包/多元的吗：

—是

↳ 文化接触是中立的吗：

—是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 960 CE - 1276 CE

↳ (在采样地区内)有暴力冲突吗：

—未知领域

↳ (与采样地区外的族群)有暴力冲突吗：

—未知领域

该宗教团体有确认入会的一般性程序/制度吗：

—是

Notes: The Chan affiliation is primarily determined by the master-disciple relations and the lineage affiliation. That requires following and becoming the disciple of a Chan master who belongs to the Chan lineage family.

↳ 与生俱来（成员身份在这种社会是默认的）：

—否

↳ 基于个人选择：

—是

↳ 由社会阶层赋予：

—否

↳ 由特定年龄阶段赋予：

—否

↳ 由性别赋予：

—是

Notes: The Chan patriarchs were predominantly male. But at the same time, there were a considerable number of female Chan practitioners and disciples. Some of the Chan nuns were able to become abbots of Chan monasteries.

Reference: Levering, Miriam L. "‘Iin-chi (rinzai) Ch’an and Gender: The Rhetoric of Equality and the Rhetoric of Heroism’". In *Buddhism, Sexuality, and Gender*. State University of New York Press, n.d..

↳ 由参与特定仪式赋予：

—是

Notes: In order to be affiliated with Chan masters, a disciple needs to be tonsured and trained in Chan monasteries. In particular, pedagogical activities between the disciple and master can be ritualized. During the rite of rushi入室 "entering the abbot's quarter," for instance, a master would have private dialogues with the disciple, often around the Chan Gong'an cases, to test if the disciple is enlightened. The dharma transmission in Chan school is also ritualized as the esoteric transmission of the monastic robe kasaya.

↳ 由其它因素而赋予：

—是: Lay people such as high officials during the Song can also be included in the Chan school as long as they could be affiliated with Chan patriarchal lineages documented in the state-sponsored flame histories.

Notes: As Brose observes for tenth-century Chan Buddhism, "Chan appears to have been conventional Buddhism organized and authenticated by means of lineage." (Brose, 91)

Reference: Brose, Benjamin. *Patrons and Patriarchs*. University of Hawaii Press, 2015.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=91cEEAAAQBAJ>.

宗教团体积极宣教、招募新成员吗：

— 是

Notes: Different from confrontational relationships among many religious sects, communications of the Chan school with other Buddhist and Confucian groups were rather open and active. Even among different sects within the Chan school, despite their varied doctrinal positions, mutual communication, rather than confrontational proselytization, characterized most of their relations.

↳ 对宗教专职人员来说，发展信众是强制性的吗：

— 否

↳ 所有信徒都必须发展信众吗：

— 否

↳ 宗教专职人员必须传道吗：

— 否

↳ 所有信众都必须传道吗：

— 否

↳ 发展信众是强制的吗：

— 否

Reference: Schlutter, Morten. *How Zen Became Zen*. University of Hawaii Press, 2010.
https://books.google.com/books/about/How_Zen_Became_Zen.html?hl=&id=WQXs14Qc8p4C.

宗教有官方的政治支持吗：

— 是

Notes: Compared to the previous dynasties, the Song court imposed more rigorous political control on all Buddhist institutions in general. The state support for Chan institutions was manifested through their sponsorship of major Chan monasteries, Chan literature, state-endorsed titles for public Chan monasteries and Chan masters. Beyond such political recognition, Buddhist communities and institutions in the territory of Song were subject to state law and tax management with their own monastic autonomy largely undermined.

Reference: Brose, Benjamin. *Patrons and Patriarchs*. University of Hawaii Press, 2015.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=91cEEAAAQBAJ>.

Reference: Kurz, Johannes. "On the Politics of Collecting Knowledge: Song Taizong's Compilation Projects". *T'oung Pao* 87, no. 4 (April 5, 2001): 289-316. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/4528879>.

Reference: Protass, Jason. "Toward a Spatial History of Chan". *Review of Religion and Chinese Society* 3, no. 2 (n.d.).

Reference: Welter, Albert. *Monks, Rulers, and Literati*. Oxford University Press on Demand, 2006. https://books.google.com/books/about/Monks_Rulers_and_Literati.html?hl=&id=v44anwEACAAJ.

↳ 神职人员由政体出资供养吗：
— 否

↳ 宗教基础设施由政体出资吗：
— 是

Notes: Major public Chan monasteries were sponsored by the polity. Besides imperial donations, the major Chan monasteries also received patronage from other groups.

↳ 政体首脑和宗教领袖是同一个人吗：
— 否

↳ 政治官员相当于宗教官员吗：
— 否

Notes: Although the political officials were not necessarily the direct religious leaders of the Chan institutions, during the Song, there was a prominent intensification of political control over religious institutions.

↳ 宗教仪式是由政体强制执行的吗：
— 是

↳ 政治律法和宗教法典大致重合：
— 是

↳ 政体提供优惠的经济待遇(比如免税)：
— 否

在该宗教中存在叛教的概念吗：
— 否

大小和结构

在样本区域中的宗教团体信奉者人数(估计人口，数字)
— 我不知道

Notes: Since the lamp histories only document Chan masters and their prominent disciples, the number of Chan adherents, in reality, was much larger than those documented. In large public monasteries in the Jiangnan region during the Southern Song dynasty, there could be as many as several thousand monks, not even including lay followers, enrolled in one monastery. However, the number of registered monks and lay followers varied dramatically in different monasteries and during different periods of time.

Reference: Schlutter, Morten. *How Zen Became Zen*. University of Hawaii Press, 2010.
https://books.google.com/books/about/How_Zen_Became_Zen.html?hl=&id=WQXs14Qc8p4C.

Reference: Protass, Jason. "A Geographic History of Song-dynasty Chan Buddhism: The Decline of the Yunmen Lineage". *Asia Major* 32, no. 1 (n.d.).

样本区域中的宗教团体的信奉者数量 (在样本区域人口中的百分比, 数字)

— 我不知道

Notes: The estimated population percentage of all Buddhist monks and nuns in the entire nation at the beginning of the eleventh century is 2.3%. The number of Chan monks could be around 1%. For more demographic information, see Song Huiyao Jigao 宋會要輯稿.

宗教团体性质【请选其一】：

— 大型宗教团体以及被公开允许的小型宗教团体

在该宗教团体中是否存在被认可的领导者：

— 是

这些领导者中有等级制度存在吗：

— 否

Notes: By "recognized leaders," this answer refers to the abbots of Chan monasteries whose names were recorded in Chan flame histories. Among the Chan abbots of the same generation, there was no noticeable hierarchy (the Chan abbots from multiple generations, however, may be subject to a master-disciple hierarchy) in terms of their religious and political status. That is because all abbots of Chan monasteries during the Song received official recognition and appointment. There were several cases where certain Chan masters enjoyed a higher prestige due to special imperial patronage (manifest through the land, tax exemption, objects, scriptures, and titles bestowed by the court). Also, different Chan abbots can enjoy varying degrees of political and economic privilege depending on the size and popularity of their monasteries.

领袖们被认为有超自然能力或者特质吗：

— 否

Notes: There were a number of eminent monks documented in Chinese hagiographies who were believed to possess supernatural powers such as sorcery, rain-making, and flood control. In general, Chan abbots during the Song, however, were more recognized by their witty dialogues with disciples, their management abilities, and their active engagement with the public and elite. In monastic practices, Chan abbots could be worshipped as comparable to

the living Buddha. That was more due to their direct dharma lineage from the Sakyamuni Buddha rather than their supernatural powers.

↳ 宗教领袖是选出来的吗：

— 是

Reference: Schlutter, Morten. *How Zen Became Zen*. University of Hawaii Press, 2010.
https://books.google.com/books/about/How_Zen_Became_Zen.html?hl=&id=WQXs14Qc8p4C.

↳ 一个领袖选择他/她自己的接班人：

— 否

Notes: During the Song, only abbots of private hereditary monasteries (usually named Vinaya Temples 律寺, although they may not necessarily belong to the Vinaya School) could choose their own disciples as replacements of the monastic leaders. Abbots of Chan monasteries did not have the power to choose their own disciples as the succeeding monastic leaders.

↳ 一个领袖的顾问团或者随从人员选择新领袖：

— 否

↳ 团体中的其他领袖选择此新领袖：

— 否

↳ 一名政治领导人选择新领袖：

— 是

Notes: As recorded in Song legal codes, the abbacy of Chan monasteries would be decided by a committee composed of local political leaders and elites. The nomination would be officially recognized and registered before being appointed as the next abbot.

↳ 该领袖领导下的其他教徒大众选择新领袖：

— 否

↳ 该采样地区的宗教团体的所有成员都参与选择新领袖：

— 否

↳ 和超自然力量的沟通被认为是选择过程的一部分：

— 否

↳ 领袖会否被认为会犯错的：

— 否

↳ 宗教领袖的门徒或亲近的追随者是否被要求顺从地且不加质疑地接受领袖在一切事务上的宣示

— 是

经典

宗教团体有经典吗：

经典是一个统称，指的是受到尊崇、与其它文本相比被认为具有特别的权威性和神圣性的文本。严格意义上经典指书写的文本，但是也存在“口述经典”（比如印度的吠陀经典）。

— 是

↳ 它们是书面的吗：

— 是

↳ 它们是口述的吗：

— 否

Notes: Although conversations and teachings of Chan masters can be transmitted orally, during the Song, such oral teachings were commonly compiled and circulated in the form of books such as yulu 語錄.

↳ 经典的来源和一个（或一组）故事有关吗：

— 是

Notes: For instance, the Platform Sutra 六祖壇經 ("Platform Sutra of the Sixth Patriarch," T48, no. 2008) is claimed to be associated with the miraculous stories of the Sixth Patriarch Huineng 惠能. According to the legend, Huineng received the secret transmission of dharma from the Fifth Patriarch 弘忍, because of his unique talent.

↳ 由至高无上的神揭示：

— 否

↳ 由其他超自然生灵揭示：

— 否

↳ 由至高无上的神启示：

— 否

↳ 由其他超自然生灵启示：

— 否

↳ 来源于神或半神半人：

— 是

Notes: The scripture is claimed to be based on the oral teachings of the sixth patriarch of Chan, the master Huineng.

↳ 来源于凡人：

— 否

↳ 这一经典是否是可以改变：

— 否

Notes: The scriptures are not alterable in terms of authentic contents. Meanwhile, similar to other Buddhist traditions, Chan literature and scripture can be interpreted and commented in varied ways.

↳ 是否存在诠释经典的正式机构（比如被宗教团体或者政治领袖所授权的机构）：

— 是

↳ 可以抛开这些机构来诠释经典吗：

— 是

Notes: Most Chan literature including the Platform Sutra was widely circulated among not only Buddhist communities but also literate laypeople. Interpretations and cultural creations based on Chan literature and scriptures could be seen in literati jottings.

↳ 只有被正式批准的人员才可以诠释经典：

— 否

↳ 是否存在一个专门被训练从事经典传布的特定群体：

— 是

↳ 是否存在一部结集的典籍经藏：

— 是

Notes: Lamp histories of Chan were codified and canonized during the Song under the sponsorship of the imperial court.

建筑，地理

是否存在纪念性的宗教建筑物：

— 否

Notes: Monumental religious architecture of major Chan monasteries in the vicinity of Hangzhou was documented by Japanese pilgrim-monks in the transmitted text 五山十刹圖. However, Chan monastic architecture dated to the Song, except for limited numbers of pagodas, has been no longer present.

有不同种类的宗教纪念性建筑物吗？

— 否

Notes: In history, there were different types of religious monumental architecture. Inside a Buddhist monastery, there were various monastic halls such as dharma hall, scripture hall, arhat hall, etc. Most monastic halls were constructed in a similar fashion in line with the Song architecture standard. Besides wood-frame halls, there were also pagodas constructed inside Chan monasteries. For architecture and furnishing inside major Chan monasteries in the vicinity of Hangzhou杭州, see the 五山十刹圖 (Jpn., Gozan jissatsu zu).

是否存在表征标志

— 是

↳ 表征在哪里显示【多选】

- 在人
- 在一些公共场所

↳ 宗教团体的表征标志有明显特色吗

— 是

Notes: One typical Chan iconography is the portraiture of Chan masters. A category of "Chan/Zen Art" has been well studied by modern art historians, including paintings and calligraphies produced associated with the Chan/Zen circles in East Asia.

Reference: Zen in China, Japan and East Asian Art, n.d..

https://books.google.com/books/about/Zen_in_China_Japan_and_East_Asian_Art.html?hl=&id=sTZ3vwEACAAJ.

Reference: Fontein, Jan, and Money L. Hickman. Zen Painting & Calligraphy, 1970.

https://books.google.com/books/about/Zen_Painting_Calligraphy.html?hl=&id=Ah1NAQAACAAJ.

↳ 眼睛（是否写实）

— 否

↳ 超自然的存在(兽形)

— 否

↳ 超自然的存在(地貌外形)

— 否

↳ 超自然的存在(人形)

— 否

↳ 超自然的存在(抽象的象征符号)

— 否

↳ 对来世的描绘

— 否

↳ 教义方面 (比如, 十字架、三位一体、密特拉教符号)

— 否

↳ 人类

— 是

↳ 表征有其它特色 :

— 是

Notes: The visual portrayals of Chan masters are usually highly naturalistic, sometimes accompanied by poems or eulogies written by elite monks or officials. In many cases, the Chan masters are depicted sitting on tall and lavish chairs, a marker of their noble status.

是否有专门的地点用于神圣行活动或者被认为是神圣的 :

— 是

Notes: There were several sites, not necessarily "sacred sites," that enjoyed unique fame in the religious landscape of Song Chan Buddhism. The most famous ones were the so-called 五山十刹 "the Five Mountains and Ten Monasteries." These Chan monasteries, which all concentrated in the lower Yangtze River region, were received superior to the other Buddhist institutions more by virtue of their official ranks and political resources instead of their religious sacredness.

↳ 神圣场地是否适应环境特点 :

"环境特点"指的是风景、山水、罗盘方位等等的特征。

— 是

Notes: Many Chan temples especially those in the Jiangnan area were located in wondrous natural landscapes, usually mountainous areas surrounded by water.

有朝圣活动吗 :

一是

Notes: During the Song period, there were pilgrim monks traveling from Japan to China, visiting and studying in major Chan monasteries in Hangzhou. The Shaolin Monastery in present-day Songshan 嵩山, Henan 河南 province was associated with the first patriarch of Chinese Chan Buddhism Bodhidharma 達摩 (act. 5-6th cent.). Although the temple was not as famous as those Five Mountains and Ten Monasteries in the lower Yangtze River region during the Song period, it is now regarded as the center of Chinese Chan Buddhism. The Shaolin Temple now attracts pilgrimages not only because of Chan Buddhism but also due to the "Shaolin Kungfu," the martial art of Shaolin whose origin was traced back to the first Chan patriarch Bodhidharma.

- ↳ 朝圣活动如何严格：
 - 可选择的（常见）

信仰

埋葬和来世

是否存在精神-肉体的区分

只有当人格（或意识）随肉体死亡而消亡时回答“否”。回答是并不一定意味着存在笛卡尔精神/肉体二元论，而只意味着人格（或意识）的一些要素在肉体死后尚存。

一是

- ↳ 精神 – 心灵被认为具有异乎其它身体部位的能力或特质
 - 是

Notes: After the death of a Chan master, his portraiture can become a unique site for the followers to build direct contact with the master's dharma and spirit. The extant Chan master portraitures reflect an innate paradox between formlessness and material as well as iconoclasm and iconization in the Chan tradition.

Reference: Faure, Bernard. *Chan Buddhism in Ritual Context*. Routledge, 2005.
https://books.google.com/books/about/Chan_Buddhism_in_Ritual_Context.html?hl=&id=RrbCSjmj5oMC.

- ↳ 精神 – 心灵被认为是非物质的，在本体论上不同于身体
 - 否

Notes: Spirit-mind is attached to materials, either through manmade portraits or through mummified bodies.

- ↳ 其它心灵-身体关系：
 - 否

对来世的信仰：

一是

Notes: Based on some Chan doctrines, once awakened to the true mind, one can get free of endless rebirths (samsara) and is no longer subject to births or deaths. In monastic practices, however, the belief in afterlife played a significant role, especially in funerary rituals.

Reference: Sharf, Robert H.. "On Pure Land Buddhism and Ch'an/pure Land Syncretism in Medieval China". *T'oung Pao* 88, no. 4 (n.d.).

↳ 该宗教团体对来世的空间位置有具体描述吗

一是

Notes: Common to other Buddhist traditions, there are six realms of the afterlife, including heaven, asura (semi-god), human, animal, hungry ghost, and purgatory.

↳ 来世在这个世界之外的特定领域空间：

一是

↳ 来世被模糊定义为“上面”的空间：

一是

↳ 来世被模糊定义为“下面”的空间：

一是

↳ 来世被模糊定义为某个平行空间：

一是

↳ 来世在“其他”空间：

一否

在这个世界上的转世

一是

↳ 以人形转世：

一是

↳ 以动物/植物的形态转世：

一是

↳ 以非生物的形态转世：

— 否

↳ 以非个体的形态转世（比如集体重生、部落、家族等等）：

— 是

Notes: There were prayers saying that they would like to be reborn as noble males.

↳ 和超越此生的因果机制有联系（比如，业力）：

— 是

↳ 这个世界中的其他形式的转世

— 否

对信众的遗体有特别处置吗：

— 是

Notes: Although it was not a common practice, a number of Chan masters' corpses were mummified for veneration during mortuary rituals and afterward. In most cases, the corpses of monks would be cremated with ashes or relics enshrined in stupas or stupa-shaped tombs.

Reference: Faure, Bernard. *The Rhetoric of Immediacy*. Princeton University Press, 2021.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=sskkEAAAQBAJ>.

↳ 火化

— 是

↳ 制成木乃伊

— 是

↳ 埋葬：

— 是

↳ 遗体被蜷屈（腿部弯曲或身体蜷缩）

— 否

↳ 遗体被伸展（或躺或卧）

— 是

↳ 遗体竖立（遗体以站姿安葬）：

— 否

↳ 遗体以其他方式安葬：

— 否

↳ 被食用：

— 未知领域

↳ 暴露放置（比如风干）：

— 否

↳ 喂动物：

— 否

↳ 二次埋葬：

— 否

↳ 遗体再处理：

— 否

↳ 其他强化(就时间或资源的耗费而言) 处理方法 [请注明]

— 是: In some cases, mummified corpses would be interred with scriptures, ashes, and organs made of cotton or silk.

埋葬过程中或者墓穴中是否存在一起殉葬现象

— 否

是否存在陪葬品：

— 未知领域

有正式的葬礼吗：

— 是

↳ 树立纪念碑：

— 否

↳ 葬于公墓：

— 是

↳ 葬于家庭墓地或教堂地下室

— 否

Notes: Monastic tomb-crypts datable to the Song period have been found, although none belong explicitly to Chan monks.

↳ 在家里（埋在房屋地下或者在有正常家庭活动的地方）

— 否

↳ 其他正式的葬礼形式：

— 是: More often, Chan monks would be buried in stupas after death. Chan masters and abbots would have their individual stupas engraved with epitaph whereas ordinary monks would be buried collectively in smaller stupas.

超自然存在

有超自然存在吗：

— 是

Notes: Even though Chan Buddhism has been characterized as iconoclasm by some doctrines, many Song Chan monasteries typically had icons of Buddhas and bodhisattvas, among the other Buddhist deities, installed in monastic halls. In other words, beliefs in supernatural beings were present in Song Chan Buddhism.

Reference: Foulk, T. Griffith. "Myth, Ritual and Monastic Practice in Sung Ch'an Buddhism". In *Religion and Society in T'ang and Sung China*, edited by Patricia Ebrey and Peter Gregory. University of Hawaii Press, n.d..

↳ 有一个至上之神存在

— 是

Notes: Among all Buddhist deities enshrined in Chan monasteries, the Buddha, most likely Sakyamuni Buddha, could be viewed as "a supreme high god." The Chan dharma family and all Chan patriarchs are viewed as the spiritual descendants of the Buddha Sakyamuni. Buddha, in this sense, could be understood as the supreme patriarch by Chan followers. Besides, Chan patriarchs were also deified during the Song as comparable to living Buddhas in this world.

↳ 至上之神是人形：

— 是

↳ 至上之神是天神

— 否

↳ 至上之神是地府的神灵（地底世界的）：

— 否

↳ 至上之神与君主不分 (王=至高的神)

— 否

Notes: Although public Chan monasteries during the Song were responsible for providing spiritual cultivation for the imperial family and praying for the emperor's longevity, there was no strong link between the Song emperors and the Chan divinity. Part of the reason could be some Song emperors were more inclined to trace their lineage back to the Daoist gods.

Reference: Schlutter, Morten. "Chan Buddhism in the Song Some Background". In *How Zen Became Zen: The Dispute over Enlightenment and the Formation of Chan Buddhism in Song-dynasty China*. University of Hawai'i Press, n.d..

Reference: Ebrey, Patricia. "Song Government Policy". In *Modern Chinese Religions (2 Vols.): Song-liao-jin-yuan (960-1368 AD)*, edited by John Lagerway and Pierre Marsone, Vol. 1. Brill, n.d..

↳ 君主被视作至上之神的表现和化身：

— 否

↳ 至上之神和精英阶层有亲属关系

— 是

Notes: Since the Chan patriarchs belong to the lineage of the spiritual descendants of Buddha Sakyamuni, all members of the Chan dharma family, sometimes including the government officials and the imperial family members, can be viewed as sharing kin relations with the Buddha.

↳ 至上之神和精英有其它类型的效忠关系

— 否

↳ 至高之神是不可质疑的善

— 否

Notes: Song Chan's attitudes toward Buddha are multifaceted. On the one hand, Song Chan masters are often depicted as Chinese Buddhas. The doctrines and practices around the ideas of "buddha-nature" and "becoming a buddha" are at the core of Chan teachings. On the other hand, however, the tradition of iconoclasm constitutes a significant part of Chan, which emphasizes the nature of emptiness and the sudden enlightenment without reliance on Buddhist deities or Buddha's teachings. In Song Chan literature, Chan masters are often depicted as irreverent, who dare to refer to the Buddha as 乾屎橛 "dry shit stick." In this sense, the Buddha in the Song Chan tradition is not unquestionably "good" as seen in other religious traditions such as Christianity.

Reference: Buckelew, Kevin. "Inventing Chinese Buddhas: Identity, Authority, and Liberation in Song-dynasty Chan Buddhism". Unpublished, PhD dissertation, Columbia

University, n.d..

Reference: Schlutter, Morten. How Zen Became Zen. University of Hawaii Press, 2010.
https://books.google.com/books/about/How_Zen_Became_Zen.html?hl=&id=WQXs14Qc8p4C.

↳ 至上之神的其他特征：

— 我不知道

↳ 至上之神具有关于这个世界的知识：

— 是

Notes: As explained above, Chan's perceptions of Buddha are multifaceted. Based on the views of "Buddha-nature" and "Buddha-mind," Buddha is not completely external to the human mind. Thus the divisions between "high god" and "you" is not as fixed as those seen in other religious traditions.

↳ 至上之神只对特定的领域的人类事务有所认知：

— 否

↳ 至上之神的知识限于采样地区的（一个或多个）特定区域：

— 否

↳ 至上之神的知识在采样地区没有限制：

— 是

↳ 至上之神的知识对采样地区以外没有限制：

— 是

↳ 不论你（在公共场所）置身何处，至上之神都可以看到你

— 否

↳ 不论你身处何处，至上之神都可以看到你（即便在黑暗中、在家里）：

— 否

↳ 至上之神可以看穿你的心/脑（隐秘的动机）：

— 是

↳ 至上之神知道你的基本特征个性（个人本质）：

— 是

- ↳ 至上之神知道你将来的人生际遇/你将来会做什么(预测的能力) :
 - 是

- ↳ 至上之神关于这个世界有其他知识 :
 - 未知领域

- ↳ 至上之神对这个世界能够有意施发因果效力 :
 - 是

- ↳ 至上之神能奖赏
 - 是

- ↳ 至上之神能惩罚 :
 - 是

- ↳ 至上之神对这个世界上可以施发间接的因果效力 :
 - 是

- ↳ 至上之神展现其积极的情感 :
 - 否

- ↳ 至上之神展现其负面的情感 :
 - 否

- ↳ 至上之神有饥饿感 :
 - 否

- ↳ 除了至高之神以外, 允许崇拜其他超自然存在吗 :
 - 是

- ↳ 至上之神具备/展现出其他一些特征 :
 - 未知领域

- ↳ 至上之神和生灵有沟通 :
 - 否

↳ 过去人的灵魂是存在的：

— 是

Notes: In the Song Chan tradition, despite its iconoclastic claims, portraits and statues of Chan masters played a significant role in Chan monastic life. These mummies, portraits, and statues were believed to be alive. Cases have been recorded that statues sweat, cried, moved, or walked. Besides, in many ritual practices such as the arhat offering and the Water-land ritual, which gained popularity in the Song Buddhist culture especially in the lower Yangtze River region, human spirits like arhats and previous sages were invited and venerated.

Reference: Foulk, T. Griffith. "Myth, Ritual and Monastic Practice in Sung Ch'an Buddhism". In *Religion and Society in T'ang and Sung China*. University of Hawaii Press, n.d..

Reference: Faure, Bernard. *The Rhetoric of Immediacy*. Princeton University Press, 2021.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=sskkEAAAQBAJ>.

Reference: Stevenson, Daniel Bruce. "Text, Image, and Transformation in the History of the Shuilu Fahui, the Buddhist Rite for Deliverance of Creatures of Water and Land". In *Cultural Intersections in Later Chinese Buddhism*. Honolulu: University of Hawai'i Press, 2001.

↳ 人类灵魂可以被看到

— 是

Notes: In popular literature and visual culture, human spirits that were invited to certain rituals could be randomly seen by the ritual participants.

↳ 人类灵魂可以用身体感触到：

— 是

↳ 过去人的灵魂对这个世界有所认知：

— 未知领域

↳ 人类灵魂至上对这个世界能够有意施发因果效力：

— 是

↳ 人类灵魂可以奖赏：

— 是

↳ 人类灵魂可以惩罚：

— 是

↳ 人类灵魂对这个世界有间接因果效应：

— 未知领域

↳ 人类灵魂对人生有记忆：

— 未知领域

↳ 人类灵魂展现出积极的情感：

— 是

↳ 人类灵魂展现出负面的情感：

— 是

↳ 人类灵魂有饥饿感：

— 是

↳ 人类灵魂有/展现出一些其他特征：

— 是: Needs to be bathed and purified during the food-offering rituals.

↳ 人类灵魂和生灵沟通：

— 是

Reference: Joo, Bong Seok. "The Arhat Cult in China from the Seventh Through Thirteenth Centuries: Narrative, Art, Space and Ritual". Unpublished, PhD dissertation, Princeton University, n.d..

↳ 在清醒状态下的日常生活中：

— 否

↳ 在睡梦中：

— 是

↳ 在被附体催眠状态中：

— 未知领域

↳ 通过占卜行为：

— 未知领域

↳ 只通过专业的宗教人士：

— 是

Notes: If we are talking about the communication between spirits and the living, then the ritual specialists are essential. There were developed ritual

manuals circulated among Chan and other Buddhist temples, providing detailed accounts of the responsibilities of ritual specialists to communicate with the invited spirits. These ritual manuals were further standardized afterwards during the Ming and Qing dynasties.

↳ 只通过君主：
— 否

↳ 其他与生灵的交流方式：
— 是: The communication may happen nonverbally. During arhat offerings, for instance, the invited arhats can express their satisfaction by transforming the tea into milky floats.

↳ 有非人类的超自然存在：
— 是

Notes: In ritual activities within (and also outside) Chan monasteries such as the Water-Land Ritual and arhat offerings, non-human spirits like ghosts are present. The following answers are primarily referring to hungry ghosts in ritual settings. (In Buddhist beliefs of the six-realms of rebirth, hungry ghosts are in a realm lesser than humans. Human spirits like Confucian and Daoist sages and past Chan patriarchs would be invited to the ritual to offer foods to non-human spirits like hungry ghosts.)

↳ 这些超自然存在可以被看到：
— 是

Notes: Similar to human spirits, as seen from extant visual materials and popular literature, non-human spirits like hungry ghosts can be seen in certain circumstances. Witnesses of such spirits were widely seen in Song-dynasty popular literature.

↳ 这些超自然存在可以用身体感触到：
— 否

↳ 非人类的超自然存在对这个世界有认知：
— 否

↳ 非人类的超自然存在对这个世界可以有意施发因果效应：
— 是

↳ 这些超自然存在可以奖赏：
— 是

↳ 这些超自然存在可以惩罚：
— 是

↳ 这些超自然存在对这个世界有间接的因果效应：
— 未知领域

↳ 这些超自然存在展现出积极的情感：
— 是

↳ 这些超自然存在展现出负面的情感：
— 是

↳ 这些超自然存在有饥饿感：
— 是

↳ 这些超自然存在有/展现出一些其他特征：
— 否

↳ 有半人半神的存在：
— 否

↳ 宗教团体具有多种超自然存在：
— 是

↳ 以基于家庭模式的亲属关系编排：
— 是

Notes: The pantheon of Chan patriarchs can be organized by kinship based on a family model, as seen in the patriarch hall in Chan monasteries.

Reference: Foulk, T. Griffith, and Robert Sharf. "On the Ritual Use of Chan Portraiture in Medieval China". In *Chan Buddhism in Ritual Context*. Routledge, n.d..

↳ 按照高下阶层编排：
— 是

Notes: The various deities invited to the Water-land ritual are organized hierarchically into two or three halls or tiers. For reference, see the work of Stevenson in Bibliography.

↳ 各自的权力是限于所属领域的：

— 是

Notes: The variety of supernatural deities shrined in Chan monasteries include Buddhas, bodhisattvas, arhats, Chan patriarchs, local deities, among others. Inside Water-land halls, there would be different kinds of supernatural beings invited to the ritual offering. For reference, see Foulk, "Myth, ritual, and monastic practice" in Bibliography.

万神庙的其他组织方式：

— 我不知道

超自然监督

是否存在超自然的监视：

“超自然监视”是指超自然存在监视人类的行为以及或者思想，特别是涉及到社会准则或潜在性违规的情况。

— 否

Notes: Although in popular literature, supernatural beings can manifest themselves to reward or punish certain behaviors, supernatural monitoring was not prominent in the Chan tradition. Chan monastic code such as 禪苑清規 did not emphasize the role of supernatural monitoring in implementing Chan monastic rules.

超自然存在施加惩罚吗：

— 未知领域

Notes: Mainstream Song Chan literature did not elaborate on the punishment by supernatural beings. However, popular literature that described ritual activities in Chan monasteries in the Lower Yangtze River region did mention the punishment from supernatural beings when certain rituals were not performed properly. See, for instance, 夷坚志, vol.1, no.24.

超自然存在赐予奖赏吗：

— 我不知道

Notes: In Chan literature, supernatural rewards were not central to the Chan ideology of the master-disciple transmission outside scriptures. In practice, however, rituals and offerings in Chan monasteries, not unlike other Buddhist schools, were conducted out of the basic belief of karma (a common belief in Buddhism literally meaning cause and effect, which can be extended to include reward and punishment). From the Song period onward, there was an increasing level of syncretism between Chan and Pure Land. Rewards of entering the western paradise after death were entailed in many Buddhist rituals, including those practiced in Chan monasteries.

救世主/末世论

是否存在救世主信仰：

— 否

Notes: Messianic beliefs were not central to Song Chan tradition, which emphasized more on enlightenment through mind-cultivation.

存在某种末世论吗：

— 否

Notes: The central ideology of Chan school is a continuous and unbroken transmission of dharma lineage outside the sutra teachings, which fundamentally counters the idea of mofa 末法, the "end of Dharam."

规范与道德现实

该宗教团体规定总体性的社会准则了吗：

— 是

该宗教团体存在传统和道德范畴的区分吗：

— 是

Notes: In recent studies on Song Chan, more attention has been put on the negotiations between a "moral" Chan tradition as recorded in the Chan literature and a "conventional" picture of Chan in the real daily monastic life.

Reference: Cole, Alan. *Patriarchs on Paper*. University of California Press, 2016.

https://books.google.com/books/about/Patriarchs_on_Paper.html?hl=&id=nisoDQAAQBAJ.

↳ 这种区别的性质是什么：

— 存在（未被强调）

↳ 宗教团体对道德规范有专门规定吗：

— 是

Notes: Answers below regarding "moral norms" are primarily referring to those prescribed by the Chan monastic codes and Chan dialogue records.

↳ 专门的道德规范和模糊的形而上学的观念模糊有不明显的联系：

— 是

↳ 专门的道德规范和模糊的形而上学的实体有明显的联系：

— 否

↳ 专门的道德规范和客观的宇宙秩序的有联系（比如业力）：

— 是

↳ 专门的道德规范以某种方式和人形的存在相联系：

— 是

Notes: Chan monastic codes were fundamentally associated with Mahayanian

bodhisattva vows (A central idea in Mahayana Buddhist tradition that a bodhisattva aspires to practice all perfections to achieve full Buddhahood for the sake of all sentient beings) and earlier Vinaya (Buddhist disciplines).

↳ 专门的道德规范和人形化的存在的命令有明显的联系：

— 是

Notes: Some moral norms can be set up by Chan masters as documented in Chan dialogue recordings.

↳ 专门的道德规范和形而上的没有特别联系：

— 是

↳ 道德规范适用于：

— 只适用于特定宗教阶层

Notes: Moral norms prescribed by Chan monastic codes and other Chan literature were mainly applied to Chan followers and specialists.

该宗教团体是否有提倡的核心重要美德：

— 否

Notes: There were no virtues advocated particularly by the Chan school. Central virtues in Chan monastic precepts are common to all Buddhist schools, such as the Five Precepts: abstention from killing, theft, sexual misconduct, falsehood, and intoxication.

常规

会员费用和惯例

该宗教团体要求成员禁欲(完全禁绝性生活)吗：

— 是

该宗教团体要求成员节制性行为(部分禁止性生活)吗：

— 否

该宗教团体要求成员阉割吗：

— 否

该宗教团体要求成员斋戒吗：

— 否

该宗教团体要求成员断除某些食物（对想吃的食物的禁忌）吗：

— 是

该宗教团体要求成员在身体上留下永久性疤痕或作疼痛的修整吗：

— 否

该宗教团体要求成员忍受疼痛的身体姿势或暂时性的伤口吗：

— 否

该宗教团体要求成年成员的牺牲生命吗

“成年”在此指该文化中主位或本土的类别；如果此类别不同于主流西方定义中的超过18周岁的并且为他/她的行为负法律责任的人类，那么请在评论/来源中注明：以下文本框。

— 否

该宗教团体要求儿童成员的牺牲吗

“儿童”在此指该文化中主位或本土的类别；如果此类别不同于主流西方定义，请在评论/来源中注明：以下文本框。

— 否

该宗教团体要求成员自我牺牲（自杀）吗：

— 否

该宗教团体要求成员贡献出财产／昂贵的物品吗：

— 否

该宗教团体要求成员奉献出自己的时间吗（例如参加会议或仪式，常规祷告等）：

— 是

该宗教团体要求成员承受身体上的风险吗：

— 否

该宗教团体要求成员接受道德戒律吗：

— 是

成为该宗教团体的成员会被组外成员边缘化吗：

— 我不知道

该宗教团体要求成员参与小规模宗教仪式（私人的，家庭的）吗：

一是

Notes: Meditation could be viewed as small-scale rituals that one can practice either communally in a monastic setting or individually in private settings.

↳ 表演间的平均时间间隔是多少（以小时计）：

这里表演指小型仪式。

— 未知领域

Notes: There were not fixed rules on the frequency of meditation practices.

该宗教团体要求成员参与大规模的宗教仪式吗：

比如，涉及两个或以上的家庭；包括有大规模的“典礼”和“节庆”。

一是

Notes: Large-scale ritual practices in Chan monasteries involved shangtang上堂, "ascending the dharma hall," where Chan abbots preached Chan teachings in front of large-scale gatherings; arhat offering 罗汉供, food offerings to arhats (supernatural Buddha's disciples); water-land rituals 水陆法会, food offerings to both invited deities and hungry ghosts to liberate all sentient beings; festivals like bodhisattva's birthday, buddha's birthday, emperor's birthday, ghost festival, among many others. As Griffith's work explains, during the Song period, rituals held in Chan monasteries were not distinct from other Buddhist schools.

↳ 平均来说，大规模的宗教仪式有多少参与者聚集在一个地点：

— 我不知道

↳ 表演间的平均时间间隔是多少（以小时计）：

这里表演指小型仪式。

— 平均间隔【小时】：120

Notes: During the Song, major ritual ceremonies were held in public Chan monasteries about six times a month, including 上堂"ascending the hall" for prayers for the emperor and the stability of the state. See Foulk, "Myth, Ritual, and Monastic Practices" for reference.

↳ 是否存在正统性审查：

正统性审查是用于保证用常规方式阐释仪式的机制。比如，通过专业祭司或者其他系统的管理的显赫监督，诉诸于详细适当阐释的文本等等。

一是

↳ 是否存在对仪轨规范性审查：

仪轨规范性审查是用于保证用常规方式阐释仪式的机制。比如，通过专业祭司或者其他系统的管理的显赫监督，诉诸于详细记载适当程序的文本等等。

一是

↳ 参与包括完全同步的修行吗：

— 是

↳ 使用酒精饮料吗：

— 否

除了仪式之外还有群内的的标示性符号吗：

比如，关于外表的特别改变，比如割礼、纹身、牺牲等等。

— 否

团体使用虚拟的亲族称谓吗：

— 否

社会与机构

社会复杂程度

对宗教团体所属社会最恰当的描述为（请选其一）：

— 一个酋邦

Notes: Song Chan institutions in the lower Yangtze River region were analogous to "chiefdoms" in terms of ranked lineages and centralized decision-making. Within each monastery, the abbot enjoyed the supreme decision-making power with several lower-rank assistants managing specific implementations. The ordinary monks were in the lower rank of the hierarchical lineage, engaging with daily monastic labors.

福利

该宗教团体提供制度化的救助饥荒的服务吗：

— 否

Notes: As documented in historical texts, during famines, Chan monasteries, like many other large Buddhist institutions, would be required by the government to provide stored food to reduce starvation. Such famine relief was more out of political order than institutionalized monastic policy.

饥荒救济是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：

— 否

该宗教团体提供制度化的的贫困救济吗：

— 否

Notes: During the Song dynasty, privatization of properties became more widespread among large Buddhist institutions, including Chan monasteries, where wealthier monks, such as abbots, might

provide loans to the other monks in poverty.

贫困救济是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：

— 否

该宗教团体对年老体弱者有制度化的关怀吗：

— 是

Notes: As documented in monastic code and historical texts, monastic elderly and infirm would be cared for by the institution. At the same time, there were also cases where dying commoners would be sent to the monastery to be taken care of by Buddhist clerics.

对年老体弱者制度化的关怀是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：

— 否

教育

该宗教团体为信众提供正规教育吗：

— 是

Notes: It was common for Buddhist monasteries to provide education to their disciples. Educational activities as documented in monastic codes include abbots' lecturing, communal reciting, and private conversations with masters.

↳ 正规教育仅限于宗教专职人员吗：

— 否

Notes: The specific forms and contents of education can vary case by case. Monastic education is a complicated field of ongoing research and debate. There were cases where secular education, such as Confucian classics, were provided in Buddhist monasteries open to both religious professionals and extra-monastic communities.

↳ 男性和女性都能得到这种教育吗：

— 未知领域

Notes: There might be females who attended education in monasteries yet were not documented in the historical literature given the number of female Chan followers during the Song.

正规教育是通过宗教团体以外的机构提供给团体信众的吗：

— 否

官僚机构

团体的信徒与团体内的官方机构有互动吗？

— 是

宗教信众与其他官僚机构有互动吗：

— 是

公共工程

该宗教团体储备公共食品吗：

— 否

Notes: There were records of Chan monasteries and other large Buddhist institutions providing food to the public during famines. Most cases, however, were under governmental orders. The food storage, therefore, was not exclusively for the public.

公共食品储备是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：

— 否

该宗教团体提供水资源管理（灌溉、防洪）吗：

— 是

Notes: One of the major roles of Buddhist temples during the Song, common to both Chan and other institutions, was to provide sacred prayer to nature for rain and good harvest. Many Buddhist icons were constructed off major rivers in the hope to control flood. There were also visual material showing water mills installed within Buddhist monasteries for irrigation.

Reference: Walsh, Michael J.. Sacred Economies. Columbia University Press, 2010.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=C9OFujPWPSQC>.

水资源管理是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：

— 否

该宗教团体提供基础交通设施吗：

— 是

Notes: Many Buddhist monasteries along major trade routes provide accommodations for traveling merchants, officials, and visitors comparable to hotels. Some large temples along major water trade routes during the Song ran businesses of water transportation as well.

Reference: 遊, 彪. 宋代寺院經濟史稿. 河北大學出版社, n.d..

Reference: Fraser, Sarah Elizabeth. 佛教物質文化: 寺院財富與世俗供養國際學術研討會論文集. 上海書畫出版社, n.d..

基础交通设施是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给团体信众的吗：

— 否

纳税

该宗教团体课取税款或什一税吗：

— 是

Notes: Buddhist temples during the Song, especially those with large economic properties (e.g. land, paddy field, woodland, etc. Such properties could be purchased by the temple or were donated by wealthy patrons.), could lend their lands to tenants. Taxes and tithes would be levied from these tenant-peasants by the monastery as part of their economy income.

Reference: Walsh, Michael J.. Sacred Economies. Columbia University Press, 2010.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=C9OFujPWPSQC>.

团体信众的税是由该宗教团体以外的机构来征收吗：

— 否

强制

该宗教团体设有体制化的警务部门吗：

— 否

宗教团体的信众与外部体制下的警务部门有互动吗：

— 是

Notes: Chan adherents would interact with the state police force outside of the monastic institutions.

该宗教团体设置体制化的法官吗：

— 否

Notes: Compared to the preceding dynasties, the Song government enhanced direct judiciary control over monastic affairs. Chan Buddhist communities, similar to commoners, were all subject to state laws and punishment.

宗教团体的信众与外部体制下的司法系统有互动吗：

— 是

该宗教团体施加制度化的处罚吗：

— 否

宗教团体的信众承受宗教团体以外的体制下的处罚吗：

— 是

Notes: For legal codes and judiciary cases, see 宋會要輯稿 and 建炎以來係年要錄 in 四庫全書.

↳ 制度化的处罚包括死刑吗：
— 是

↳ 制度化的处罚包括流放吗：
— 是

↳ 制度化的处罚包括体罚吗：
— 是

↳ 制度化的处罚包括排挤孤立吗：
— 是

↳ 制度化的处罚包括没收财产吗：
— 是

该宗教团体有正式的法典吗：

— 否

Notes: Chan institutions would adhere to Chan monastic codes compiled by renowned Chan masters. These monastic codes did not serve as legal codes during the Song.

宗教团体的信众受制于外部体制下的法典吗：

— 是

Notes: For historical documents of Song-dynasty legal codes and cases, see 宋會要 and 建炎以來係年要錄.

福利

该宗教团体有体制化的军事力量吗：

— 否

宗教团体的信众参加宗教团体以外机构提供的机制化的军事力量吗：

— 否

宗教团体的信众受保护或受治于宗教图案以外机构提供的机制化的军事力量吗：

— 是

书面语

该宗教团体有自己独特的书面语吗：

— 否

Notes: The Chan Buddhism was commonly viewed as a fully "sinicized" Buddhist school in terms of ideology, literature, ritual liturgy, and art. The use of other written languages such as Sanskrit was not usual among Chan institutions. Most scriptures that the Chan institutions engaged with, including those that might contain dharani spells, were written exclusively in Chinese.

团体信众能在宗教团体以外的体制中接触到非宗教专用的书面语吗：

— 否

团体信众在宗教团体以外的体制下使用非宗教专用的书面语吗：

— 否

日历

该宗教团体有正式的历法吗：

— 否

该宗教团体的信众在宗教团体以外的体制下有正式的历法可用吗：

— 是

Notes: The calendar used by religious institutions during the Song was to a large extent in compliance with the state calendar.

食物生产

该宗教团体自产食物吗

— 是

请描述食物生产的形式/层级 [多选]：

— 畜牧

— 大规模农业（比如，单一型农业作物制，组织化的灌溉系统）

— 其他【请在评论中说明】

Notes: donation from patrons, trade, and loans, among other means.

该宗教团体外的机构向团体信众提供食物吗：

— 否

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